

Chapter 57

Current Trends in the Study of Indian Knowledge Systems

Souvik Adhikari^a & Samarjit Dey^b

^aLibrarian, Rajendra Academy for Teachers' Education

Email Id adhikarisouvik453@gmail.com

^bResearch Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science, Vidyasagar University

Email Id samarjitdey9@gmail.com

Abstract

Indigenous knowledge is accumulated, practiced, and orally transcribed from generation to generation. Indian knowledge varies from region to region and between ethnic groups. The Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge (IJTK) plays a vital role in documenting and disseminating indigenous knowledge. It is a reviewed quarterly Indian publication started by CSIR-NISCAIR in 2002. This journal covered undocumented literature and research papers on indigenous knowledge. This paper analyzes the research papers published in the Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge (IJTK) during 2020-2024, research trends of different types of traditional knowledge (Agriculture, Ayush, Biodiversity, Ethnobotany, Food Science, Nutrition, Pharmacology, etc.), these various types area were introduced in their publications in 2019. A total of 545 publications' bibliographic data was collected from <http://op.niscair.res.in/index.php/IJTK/issue/archive> for this study. Year-wise publications in different types of areas, keyword occurrences, and other related parameters are analyzed to visualize the research trends. Find out that 126 publications were published on Pharmacology/Ethnomedicine, 94 on Agriculture, and 82 on Ayush. The maximum number of articles are published in 2021, 123 publications. Also, 2792 keywords are retrieved from the 545 publications for this study. Traditional knowledge keywords are used in 37 publications, Medicinal plants are used in 21 publications and Antioxidants are used in 20 publications. This study will be helpful for researchers of indigenous knowledge in understanding the research trends of this core area.

Keywords: Indian knowledge system, Research trends, Traditional knowledge

1 Introduction

Indian knowledge System also known as the Indigenous knowledge system of India refers to the cumulative wisdom, skills, and practices passed down through generations within specific communities, often rooted in their cultural and environmental context. The Indian Knowledge System (IKS) is an extensive framework of knowledge that has evolved over thousands of years, including many domains such as philosophy, science, medicine, and spirituality, with significant contributions to mathematics, astronomy, and metaphysics. The Indigenous knowledge system of India is based on Vedic literature, the Upanishads, the Vedas, and the Upavedas. The Indian Knowledge System's primary goals are to encourage and promote additional study in several areas to address current societal problems.

Various types of research and publications are being conducted around the world for the sustainable development of specific areas of traditional knowledge. Various initiatives such as R&D laboratories, databases, and IKS cells are established to innovate, preserve, and disseminate traditional knowledge. Nowadays, many portals have been created that store rich knowledge related to IKS, and these are open to everyone. Financial support is provided for research activities, workshops, seminars, and publications

to draw public attention to traditional knowledge and to develop IKS. The main focus of this study reveals the trends of IKS over time.

The periodical, *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*, has been chosen to conduct this research. It is a renowned source that transcends the indigenous knowledge of India to the community. CSIR-NIScPR (erstwhile NISCAIR), New Delhi has published this periodical since 2002 and it was first indexed in SCI in 2009. It has transitioned from a quarterly replacement to a monthly frequency since 2024. According to JCR 2021, the impact factor of this journal is 1.091. This periodical is listed in several significant international databases, including CAB International (UK), Food Science and Technology Abstracts (UK), National Information Technical Service (USA), MANTIS Database (USA), MAPA (India), ISA (India), and others. Since 2009, the journal has been open access, and the complete text of recent issues and archives is available via <http://nopr.niscair.res.in>, the CSIR-NISCAIR repository. It is a prominent platform that publishes notable articles related to India's traditional knowledge. The *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge* will publish original research papers, review articles, brief communications, and other materials that focus on the observation and experimental study of the biological activities of plant, animal, and mineral materials used in traditional medical systems like Ayurveda, Siddha, Yoga, Unani, Naturopathy, Homoeopathy, and folk remedies. The research study analyses this journal from several perspectives such as publication distribution of different areas, keyword occurrence, different tribal communities, etc.

2 Literature Review

This study examines the roles and objectives of Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) within the Indian context. It also explores the delivery of IKS courses through digital platforms, the development of modules and adaptations for training educators to improve the quality of IKS course delivery, and the creation of teacher training centers focusing on specific IKS topics. The research highlights various initiatives by higher education institutions, such as Grand National Challenges, National Competitions, Hackathons, and efforts to incentivize innovation. Furthermore, this study aims to promote Indian heritage both within India and globally through IKS. (Mandavkar, 2023) TKDL is seen as a potential factor in the management of patent law. This study examines the TKDL database as a repository of indigenous medical knowledge in India. It highlights the significant role TKDL can play in the international patent classification system. The study also emphasizes that the TKDL database is a crucial resource for research on traditional knowledge. (Fredriksson, 2023) This study examines the increasing recognition and publication of the journal '*Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*.' It analyzes the journal across various factors, including publication and citation counts, citation distribution, affiliation data, tribal community representation, and keyword-related issues. The findings reveal that 16 articles have received 20 or more citations, while 9 journals have an impact factor exceeding 10. Additionally, the study identifies 27 Indian tribes and 206 tribes worldwide. (Pathak & Bharati, 2018) Scientometrics, like many other journal evaluation tools, employs a set of indicators to assess journals in various ways. This study analyzes the publications of the *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge* to evaluate its scientific research output. A total of 938 articles, published between 2002 and 2012, were identified and examined using different indicators, including article distribution per year, authorship patterns, author collaborations, citation counts, keyword analysis, and country-wise publications. The results revealed that the highest number of publications occurred in 2010 (139 articles), while the lowest was in 2003 (10 articles). Additionally, the study found that, on average, 24 articles were published per issue during the period from 2002 to 2012. (Shivakumaraswamy & Muthuraj,

2017) This research presents a quantitative analysis of the research articles published in the *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge* from 2014 to 2020. A total of 705 articles were selected for the study and analyzed using various scientometric techniques, including article distribution, journal growth rate, author productivity, collaboration degree, and the geographical distribution of articles at the city, state, and country levels. The findings reveal that 2020 saw the highest number of articles published (106). Of the 705 articles, 31 were authored by single contributors. The study also indicates an average of 29.29 citations per paper. Additionally, India ranked first in terms of article contributions by country. (Gupta, n.d.) This study explores the impact evaluation of open access (OA) journals using various indicators. These indicators are categorized into two groups: citation indicators (such as H-index, CiteScore, and Scimago journal rank), which assess the citation impact of journals, and open metric indicators (including news mentions, blog mentions, Twitter mentions, policy mentions, patent mentions, etc.), which measure the broader open metrics of journals. The findings of this research suggest that both citation indicators and open metric indicators play a crucial role in the development of OA journals. (Wei, 2020) Open-access journals significantly influence researchers. This study examines LIS open-access journals indexed in the Social Science Citation Index. A total of 36 journals were selected and analyzed based on various criteria, including the availability of the journal's website, total number of articles, access to full-text content, publication frequency, and impact factor. The findings reveal that five journals publish more than 100 articles annually, with Scientometrics leading with 254 articles. Meanwhile, the Journal of Informatics had the highest impact factor at 4.153, and the Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology had the highest citation count, with 4,613 total citations. (Chen & Du, 2016) This research focuses on the content analysis of journals related to distance education. Seven journals were selected for the study, which illustrates the trends in distance education over time. The primary objective is to conduct a content analysis of these journals from various perspectives, including research areas, theoretical and conceptual frameworks, methodologies, models, strategies, and data collection and analysis techniques. Additionally, the study examines the distribution of keywords and identifies the most cited authors in the field of distance education. Ultimately, the results of this research aim to highlight potential areas for further exploration and identify overlooked topics within distance education research. (Bozkurt et al., 2015) Journal evaluation is a crucial aspect of bibliometric research, playing a key role in understanding the evolving trends within a subject over time. Various indicators are employed to assess journals. This study focuses on the evaluation of scholarly journals using panel data analysis, with the primary objective being the selection of appropriate indicators for evaluating journals within specific areas. The findings highlight that panel data analysis is an effective method for determining suitable indicators for journal assessment, as the same set of indicators may not be applicable across different academic fields. (Yu et al., 2009) The primary goal of this study is to promote the use of the CERIF data model for storing journal impact factors and scientific areas. One of the key components of the CERIF model is the CRIS UNS system, which is utilized here for journal assessment. Consequently, this paper argues that the CERIF data model serves as a valuable tool for efficiently evaluating journals. (Ivanovic et al., 2012) The rapid growth of publications today makes their evaluation crucial. This paper emphasizes several indicators that aid in assessing journals. It also explores the characteristics of high-quality journals and clarifies various concepts related to impact factors and citation databases. Ultimately, the paper suggests that journals should be evaluated for quality based on different purposes, and the evaluation results rely on specific indicators. (Rousseau, 2002)

3 Scope

To understand the current research trends in the Indian knowledge system, here selected the Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge (IJTK) for this study. Publications of the Indian knowledge system are mostly published in IJTK, and it is a core journal of the Indian knowledge system. It highlights major milestones achieved by the Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge from having a modest beginning as one of India's first journals on traditional knowledge to its development into becoming one of India's top journals in this field.

The periodical, Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge (IJTK) published by CSIR-NIScPR (erstwhile NISCAIR) is considered one of the most comprehensive repositories of India's Indigenous knowledge systems. The link to access the research papers of this journal is mentioned in the methodology section of this article. Since 2002, this journal has been promoting the Indian knowledge system both in India and internationally for twenty-four remarkable years. The IJTK publishes original research papers, review articles, and short communications, and more, focused on the observation and experimental analysis of the biological properties of materials from plants, animals, and minerals used in traditional healthcare systems. As per JCR 2022, the impact factor of this journal is 0.8 and it is indexed in several national and international databases. The Scimago Journal Ranking (SJR) has ranked the journal in the category of Complimentary and Manual Therapy, there are only 12 global journals and IJTK ranks 4th and it is the only journal from the Asiatic region.

4 Objectives

The main research objectives are as follows:

- i. To study the year-wise distribution of articles published in IJTK;
- ii. To examine area-wise research trends of articles of IJTK;
- iii. To identify and analyze the contributions of leading authors in the IJTK journal;
- iv. To analyze the frequency and distribution of keywords in the articles.

5 Research Methodology

This paper analyzes the research papers published in the Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge (IJTK) during 2020-2024. Research trends of different types of traditional knowledge (Agriculture, Ayush, Biodiversity, Ethnobotany, Food Science, Nutrition, Pharmacology, etc.), these different types were introduced in their publications in 2019. The bibliographic data was collected from <http://op.niscair.res.in/index.php/IJTK/issue/archive> for this study manually and entered in MS Excel. A total of 545 publications are collected for that period. Three types of documents are published in those issues, only research articles are selected for this study. The articles are analyzed by year of publication, area-wise research trends, keyword occurrences, and contributed authors.

6 Results and Discussions

Table 1 represents the year-wise distributions along with area-wise publications. Below table 1 shows the year-wise distribution from 2020 to 2024 along with different areas. Areas were introduced in the year 2019 in their archive's portal, different areas are introduced as per requirement on different issues. In this 5 years' study, the highest number of articles were published in the year 2021, and the least in 2023. Up to 2023 journal's frequency was quarterly, in 2024 it changed its frequency to monthly. Average articles are published in the quarterly period of 25 to 31 per issue and in the monthly issues 10

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articles. The highest 126 publications are published on Pharmacology/Ethnomedicine. Also, 94 on Agriculture, 82 on Ayush, 76 on Ethnobotany, and so on. Observing that publications on Food Science and Nutrition are decreasing over the years and fluctuating the others.

Table 1 Area & Year wise distribution of publications

Area	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Total
Pharmacology/Ethnomedicine	29	24	30	21	22	126
Agriculture	4	24	20	26	20	94
Ayush	14	19	18	14	17	82
Ethnobotany	20	21	11	8	16	76
Food Science and Nutrition	18	14	13	12	11	68
Biodiversity	12	5	3	1	5	26
Zoology	3	2	2	5	1	13
Microbiology	1	3	3	3	1	11
Handicrafts	1	1	0	2	4	8
Forestry	0	0	3	1	0	4
Natural Dyes	0	0	0	1	0	1
Others	3	10	1	9	13	36
Total	105	123	104	103	110	545

Table 2 represents keyword occurrences; a total of 2776 keywords are used in 545 publications over 5 years' time span. The average number of keywords is 5.09, here are listed mostly used keywords, which have occurred more than 10 times within this period. Traditional knowledge keywords were used in 37 publications over the years, medicinal plants used in 21 publications, antioxidant in 20, ethnobotany in 18, and so on. These keywords represent the publication, and what types of research articles are published in that journal.

Table 2 Keywords Occurrences

Rank	Keywords	Occurrences
1	Traditional knowledge	37
2	Medicinal plants	21
3	Antioxidant	20
4	Ethnobotany	18
5	Ethnomedicine	17
6	Traditional medicine	16
7	Traditional	14
8	Antioxidant activity	13
8	Indigenous knowledge	13
9	Conservation	12
9	HPTLC	12
10	Ayurveda	11

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10	COVID-19	11
10	Phytochemicals	11

Table 3 represents the author list, who contributed more to this IJTK journal. Authors are the pillar of publications, they contribute more to the different fields to enrich the research repositories. Here are the top authors with their affiliation, who have 7 and more than 7 publications in this journal in that time span. The highest 13 publications are contributed by Santosh Kumar from ICAR Patna, 11 by A. Kumar from RARI Itanagar and Rajendra K. Singh from Dankook University.

Table 3 Top contributed author list with affiliation

Rank	Authors	Affiliation	No. of Publications
1	Santosh Kumar	ICAR Research Complex for Eastern Region- PATNA	13
2	A. Kumar	Regional Ayurveda Research Institutes- Itanagar	11
2	Rajendra K. Singh	Dankook University	11
3	Surender Singh	AIIMS New Delhi	8
4	Anand Kumar Chaudhary	Banaras Hindu University Institute of Medical Sciences- VARANASI	7
4	Prashant Kaushik	Universitat Politecnica de Valencia	7
4	Pramod Kumar	Indian Agricultural Research Institute	7
4	V.K. Yadav	Ranchi University	7

7 Conclusions

This study shows the research trends of different areas-wise publications of the Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge (IJTK) from 2020 to 2024, mostly during the time of COVID-19 and the post-COVID-19 era. A total of 545 publications' bibliographic data retrieved from the archives portal, used the archives portal instead of any bibliographic databases because of the area-wise publication distributions. Observed that IJTK used 11 different areas to scatter the publications, on that period. Here try to find out the area-wise research trends, and also find out the impact of change in the frequency on the number of publications. In 2023 highest 123 research articles are published, and most of the publications are published in the Pharmacology/Ethnomedicine and Agriculture areas. In the keyword occurrences, most of the publications used traditional knowledge and medicinal plants keywords. Santosh Kumar contributed the highest number of 13 publications within this period. Here, it is concluded that, in the era of Artificial Intelligence and modern science, the research and implementation of indigenous knowledge have kept its usefulness the same over the years.

References

Bozkurt, A., Akgun-Ozbek, E., Yilmazel, S., Erdogan, E., Ucar, H., Guler, E., Sezgin, S., Karadeniz, A., Sen-Ersoy, N., Goksel-Canbek, N., Dincer, G. D., Ari, S., & Aydin, C. H. (2015). Trends in distance education research: A content analysis of journals 2009-2013. *The International*

- Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 16(1).
<https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v16i1.1953>
- Chen, M., & Du, Y. (2016). The status of open access library and information science journals in SSCI. *The Electronic Library*, 34(5), 722–739. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EL-05-2015-0070>
- Fredriksson, M. (2023). India's Traditional Knowledge Digital Library and the Politics of Patent Classifications. *Law and Critique*, 34(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10978-021-09299-7>
- Gupta, S., & Sahu, R. K. (2021). Scientometric Analysis of Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge (IJTK), 2014-2020. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.
<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6089>
- Ivanovic, D., Surla, D., & Rackovic, M. (2012). Journal evaluation based on bibliometric indicators and the CERIF data model. *Computer Science and Information Systems*, 9(2), 791–811.
<https://doi.org/10.2298/CSIS110801009I>
- Kolle, S. R. (2016). Publication trends in Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge: a bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Advances in Library Sciences*, 3(2), 25-34.
- Mandavkar, P. (2023). Indian Knowledge System (IKS). *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4589986>
- Pathak, M., & Bharati, K. A. (2018). Growing visibility and impact of Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*, 17(3).
<http://nopr.niscpr.res.in/handle/123456789/44596>
- Rousseau, R. (2002). Journal evaluation: technical and practical issues. *Library Trends*, 50(3), 418–439.
- Shivakumaraswamy, K. N., & Muthuraj, T. N. (2017). Indian journal of traditional knowledge: A scientometric study (2002–2012). *International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology*, 7(3), 182. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2249-5576.2017.00020.6>
- Wei, M. (2020). Research on impact evaluation of open access journals. *Scientometrics*, 122(2), 1027–1049. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03306-6>
- Yu, L., Shen, X., Pan, Y., & Wu, Y. (2009). Scholarly journal evaluation based on panel data analysis. *Journal of Informetrics*, 3(4), 312–320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2009.04.003>